

Estimating prevalence and population size of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olive cultivars with differential phenotypic responses to the bacterial infection

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Prevalence and bacterial population size of *Xylella fastidiosa* (*Xf*) were studied in multivarietal olive groves located in the demarcated infected area of Apulia (southern Italy), under high natural pressure of inoculum.

Surveys to assess the occurrence of typical *Xylella*-induced symptoms and the prevalence of infections included the cultivars Ogliarola salentina, Coratina, Frantoio, FS17 and Leccino. Results showed that infection rates varied according to the cultivar, being 40-60% for FS17 and Leccino, respectively, and close to 90% for the remaining cultivars. On a subset of 12 infected olives/cultivar, inspections and sampling were performed in 4 different period of the year, with leaf and xylem tissues tested separately. Symptoms of dessication at the beginning and end of the experiment, scored on a scale of 0 (not present) to 5 (severe), ranged from 4.5 to 5 for Ogliarola salentina, from 3 to 4.5 for Coratina, from 1,5 to 3 for Frantoio, and from 0.5 to 1 for FS17 and Leccino. Diagnostic tests showed that: (i) the bacterial populations of Leccino and FS17 were consistently lower than those of Ogliarola salentina and Coratina (on average 105 vs 107 CFU/g), regardless the period and the tissue; (ii) the bacterium was readily detected (up to 100% of diagnostic accuracy) in the most symptomatic cultivars (Ogliarola salentina and Coratina), regardless the period of sampling and the tissues used; (iii) for Frantoio, FS17 and Leccino, the highest values of diagnostic accuracy were obtained using xylem tissues, without significant differences among the sampling periods; (iv) in FS17 the use of leaf tissues yielded the lowest level of detection accuracy in most of the sampling periods; (v) the trees of Frantoio showed an intermediate behaviour, both for symptoms and bacterial population size.

These results show that quantitative measures of *Xylella* populations correlates with the phenotypic responses to *Xf*, and may help to predict, before the onset of symptoms, the degree of susceptibility of a given olive genotype. Important information for the detection of the bacterium in olives were also obtained.

Keywords: Bacterial population; susceptibility; *Xylella*